

Review Article

Petroleum Profit and Excise Duties Taxes as Determinants of Economic Development in Nigeria

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Abstract

This paper investigated the extents to which petroleum profit and excise duties taxes serve as determinants of Nigerian economic development. Ex-post facto research design was used and secondary was obtained from the Central Bank of Nigeria statistical bulletin from 1993-2023. Data obtained were analyzed using autoregressive distributed lag and error correction mechanism statistical tools. Findings indicated that while petroleum profit tax significantly negatively determines Nigerian economic development (gross domestic product per capita), excise duties tax significantly positively determines Nigerian economic development (gross domestic product per capita). The implications of the findings are that while excise duties tax is adequately managed, petroleum profit tax is inadequate managed, hence the reason for the negative on Nigerian economic development. On the basis of the finding, the study recommends among others of the need to strengthen the supervision and collection of petroleum profit tax and the efficient management of profits from petroleum companies. More so, there is the need to avert misuse/misallocation of revenues from petroleum profit tax in order to positively enhance Nigerian economic development.

Keywords: Economic development, economic growth, excise duties, petroleum profit tax, Nigeria, tax revenue.

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Introduction

Over the years, Nigeria has experienced growth in gross domestic product (GDP); however, GDP growth has not resulted in socioeconomic development (Ososuakpor & Okoro, 2023; Imasuen, Okoro & Yahaya, 2022). More so, increase in poverty, unemployment and poor health persists regardless of the numerous reforms in the country (Adefolake & Omodero, 2022; Demaki, Eromafuru & Imasuen, 2021; Odiri, Aruoren & Okoro, 2021; Obasanmi & Imasuen, 2020). Evidence suggests that the contribution of tax revenue to government's total revenue still remains low (Okoro & Ekwueme, 2018; Adeyeye, 2019; Nyoni, 2019; Awa & Ibeanu, 2020). Tax is one of the elements a government can use in providing basic amenities and growing an economy; taxes are of various forms- petroleum profit, excise duties, companies' income, personal income, value added taxes, among others. However, this study focused on revenues from petroleum profit and excise duties taxes.

Theoretically, tax revenues should enhance national development by stimulating growth in GDP and creating an environment conducive to sectoral openness and activities. There are numerous views on whether revenues from petroleum profit and excise duties in Nigeria have effectively driven the desired socioeconomic development. Studies have revealed that researchers have attempted to measure economic benefits of tax revenue in numerous ways (Odu, 2022; Olaoye, Ogundipe & Oluwadare, 2019; Akpubi & Igbekoyi, 2019; Ofurum, Amaefule, Okonya & Amaefule, 2018). Notably, there is substantial literature that had examined the relationship between tax revenue and economic growth (GDP per capita) in developed countries like United States of America (USA), United Kingdom (UK), among others.

In contrast, there are few studies that had addressed the likely relationship between tax revenue measures (excise duties and petroleum profit taxes) and GDP per capita) in Nigeria; thus, economic growth is a major issue that requires consideration. In contemporary society, growth is required for any institution to go forward. Additionally, most prior studies had treated tax revenue in segmented ways, failing to distinguish between GDP and economic development comprehensively; these studies were limited in scope and often not directly measuring GDP per capita. Scientific research on petroleum profit, excise duties taxes and economic development (GDP per capita) nexus remain inadequate in Nigeria.

While prior studies had focused on tax revenue and economic growth and development, none had comprehensively addressed the combination of tax revenue variables like petroleum profit and excise duties taxes in a single study. These studies did not consider GDP per capita. Hence, this study investigated the extents to which petroleum profit and excise duties taxes serve as major determinants of Nigerian economic development from 1993-2023

Review of Related Literature

Petroleum Profit Tax (PPT)

In Nigeria, companies involved in petroleum operations are subjected to tax under the Petroleum Profit Tax Act (PPTA) of 1959 (as amended). Petroleum profit tax (PPT) applies to the extraction and transportation of petroleum or chargeable oil within Nigeria by or on behalf of a company, excluding refining activities as part of a company's business operation (Odu, 2022). PPT also covers any incidental operations and sale or disposal chargeable oil by or on behalf of a company (Okoro & Egberi, 2020; Okoro & Egberi, 2019).

According to Imasuen (2024); Imasuen, (2023) revenue from oil sale serves as a key mechanism for distributing wealth between the host government and the international oil companies (IOCs). It is a direct tax levied yearly on the net profits of a petroleum taxpayer engaged in exploration and production activities (Awa & Ibeanu, 2020). The administration of PPTA in Nigeria has predominantly focused on revenue generation rather than stimulating economic growth and development (Okoro & Egbunike, 2017). Adefolake and Omodero (2022) emphasized that the oil sector is vital to the Nigerian economy and its sustainability is imperative for realizing economic growth.

Notably, the institutional capacity to administer PPT effectively in Nigeria is lacking (Okoro & Ekwueme, 2020; Okerekeoti & Okoro, 2021). PPT applies to companies engaged in petroleum operations, including exploration, development, production and the sale of crude oil (Sinebe & Okoro, 2023). It also covers transportation of crude oil via pipeline to port of export, but excludes transportation by ocean-going vessels from the point of export to international markets.

Custom and Excise Duties (CED)

In Nigeria, custom and excise duties (CE) represent one of the ancient forms of modern tax revenue with their origins dating back to 1860. CED are levied on goods imported into the country and are charged either as a percentage of the value of import or as a fixed amount on the basis of the quantity (Adefolake & Omodero, 2022). CED is a vital source of revenue for the federal government, and payable by importers of specified goods. CED was introduced in Nigeria in 1962 to diversify the revenue base of the federal government.

Both custom and excise duties are vital components of non-oil revenue and have been vital sources of revenue both before and after the discovery of crude oil in Nigeria; hence, CED have significantly contributed to national development. Import duties also known as custom duties, tariff, import tax or import tariffs, are collected by a country's customs authorities on imported goods.

According to Veiga and McCahery (2019); Kaneva, Chugunov, Pasichnyi, Andriy and Husarevych (2022). Import duties serve two (2) main purposes: generating income for the government and providing competitive advantage to locally produced goods that are not subject to CED. In addition, high import duties may be used to penalize a country by making their products more expensive.

Economic Development

Economic development has been used to describe persistent annual increase in a country's real national income. As observed by Shobowale, Olopade, Eseyin and Biyi (2023), economic development implies yearly trends in net national product (at constant prices). Imide and Dania (2019) believed that economic developments should embrace rise in standard of living, national product and incomes. Thus, economic development can be viewed as increase in real per capita income over a period of time; this view appears to be widely supported in the literature (Ojima & Anyanwu, 2021; Raymond & Ekponaanuadum, 2021).

Traditionally, economic development can be measured as GDP; although other economic development metrics like gross national product and human development index have been employed often in the literature (Amadi & Alolote, 2019; Awogbemi, 2023). As observed by Eze (2023), if economic development is measured in terms of population, it can be denoted as real per-capita income. Hence, economic development is also seen as annual increase in per-capita income (i.e. real GDP per-capita). Numerous measures have been advanced to enhance economic development namely, increasing the amount of physical capital goods; and productivity (Eniekezimene, Wodu & Anda-Owei, 2023). In addition to the above, Isola and Alani (2022) suggest that improvement in technology can attract increase in economic development because it can offer people to produce additional outputs with same inventory of capital goods.

Furthermore, the decline in economic development in Nigeria have been linked to several dynamics which include but not limited to poor tax administration of petroleum profit, company income and other tax variants, human capital flight, violence, terrorism; however, this study was hinged on two (2) of the identified dynamics – petroleum profit and excise duties taxes as they determine economic development in Nigeria.

Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on the Wagner law of increasing state activity theory (WLSAT). The theory posits that government activities and expenditures tend to increase as a country's progresses via industrialization and economic development. WLSAT empirical analysis of in the late 19th century led proponent of the theory to conclude that real income per capita rises and proportion of public spending relative to total expenditures grows due to efficient tax administration and collection mechanisms (He, Ren & Taffler, 2019). Thus, the theorist advocated that emergence of a modern tax system would lead to greater socioeconomic growth and development.

Wagner identified three (3) primary reasons for expansion of a country's expenditure; replacement of private sector activities (administrative and protective roles that expand with economic development); provision of cultural and welfare services (education, public health, retirement pension, food subsidies, disaster relief, environmental protection, etc.); as well as technological change and monopolies (Prichard, Custers, Dom, Daveport & Roscitt, 2019).

The theory asserts that as per capita income increases, relative size of the public sector also increases. Therefore, the theorist categorized government expenditures into three (3) main areas: administration and defense; cultural and welfare functions; and provision of direct services in areas of market failure (Bradshaw, Liao & Ma, 2019; and Wang, Xu, Sun & Cullinan, 2020). The theory accounts for the growing ratio of government expenditure via taxation.

Research Methods

In this study, *ex-post facto* research design was employed and secondary data was sourced from National Bureau of Statistics (NBS), Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) statistical bulletin, and Federal Inland Revenue Service (FIRS). The choice of design is hinged on the fact that the study seeks to examine already existing conditions where the variables of the study cannot be manipulated. Data on petroleum profit tax and excise duties taxes (tax revenue measures) and gross domestic product per capita (economic development measure) were obtained as yearly times series from 1993-2023.

The yearly time series data obtained were analyzed by means of descriptive statistics (scores obtained from mean, median, minimum, maximum, standard deviation, kurtosis and skewness) and inferential statistics (Augmented Dickey-Fuller-ADF; Autoregressive Distributed Lag –ARDL; Error Correction Mechanism-ECM; Granger Causality tests). The statistical analysis was carried out via STATA 16.0 software. The functional form of the model is given as:

$$GDPPC = f(PPT, CEDT) \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

$$GDPPC_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 PPT_t + \beta_2 CEDT_{t-1} + \mu_t \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

Where: GDPPC is Gross Domestic Product per Capita; PPTPC is = Petroleum Profit Tax Revenue per Capita; CEDT is Custom and Excise Duty per Capita; β_0 is Constant Parameter; β_1 , β_2 are Estimation Parameters; μ is Error term; t is Time dimension. A-priori expectations are that $\beta_1 > 0$, $\beta_2 > 0$.

Empirical Results

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics

	GDPPC	PPT	CEDT
Mean Score	30374.2	2573.696	278.6421
Median Score	242900.8	1973.275	25.15000
Maximum score	781331.3	6549.950	4957.650
Minimum Score	16732.00	14.47000	8.300000
Standard deviation	253837.0	2306.548	936.2506
Skewness	0.500024	0.447645	4.696913
Kurtosis	1.904342	1.672008	23.96673
Probability	0.500024	0.223955	0.000000

Table 1 presents a summary of descriptive trends of the variables; average GDP per capita (GDPPC) is N303,074.2; this suggests that on the average, the each Nigerian has a mean annual income of N303,074.2; however, this value translates to a daily income that is below the globally accepted poverty line of N500 per person per day. The peak GDP per capita value reached N781,331.3 in 2021; this significant increase may be attributed to inflationary pressures, particularly as the Naira depreciated considerably against US dollar. Depreciation has likely inflated nominal income values without necessarily reflecting real improvements in living standards. Nigeria's per capita income has experienced considerable fluctuations over the study period, as evidenced by a high standard deviation of 253,837. This variability highlights the significant instability in Nigeria's economy, with periods of both growth and contraction.

The positive skewness of 0.500024 in GDP per capita distribution suggests an upward trend in income levels, possibly driven by inflationary trends rather than actual increase in economic productivity or wealth distribution. Kurtosis value of 1.904342 is greater than 1; it indicates a leptokurtic distribution, meaning that the income distribution has a higher peak and fatter tails than a normal distribution. This reflects the presence of extreme values and rapid changes in income levels during the study period.

Jarque-Bera test statistic, with a significance value of 0.277021 indicates that the GDP per capita data is normally distributed over the observed period. This normality in distribution suggests that the fluctuations in income per capita, despite being significant, follow a pattern that is statistically typical of economic data over time.

Petroleum profit tax has an average value of N2,573; this indicates that on the average, the annual tax revenue from petroleum profits remitted to the government is N2,573.6 per capita. The trend analysis revealed a positive skewness value of 0.448, suggesting a progressive increase in revenue from petroleum profit tax over time. This positive skewness reflects a gradual and consistent rise in the revenue base from this tax source. Kurtosis value of 1.67 indicates that growth in petroleum profit tax per capita has been rapid and steady, pointing to increasingly significant contribution of this revenue source to the government's coffers. The kurtosis value, being greater than 1 suggests leptokurtic distribution, which is characterized by a sharper peak and fatter tails compared to a normal distribution, which signifies periods of accelerated revenue growth.

Furthermore, Jarque-Bera test yields a significance value of 0.223955, which is above the 0.05 threshold. This suggests that the distribution of petroleum profit tax per capita is normally distributed, implying that the variations in this tax revenue over time follow a statistically typical pattern. Overall, the data indicates that petroleum profit tax per capita has been on a steady increase over the years, contributing progressively to Nigeria's non-oil revenue, and showing a stable and predictable pattern of growth.

Customs and excise duties have an average value of N278.6 over the study period. This indicates that, on average, the annual tax revenue from customs and excise duties remitted to the government is N278.6 per capita. The data reveals a positive skewness value of 4.696913, indicating a significant and progressive increase in revenue from this source over time. High skewness value suggests that the growth in customs and excise duties per capita has not been uniform, with more substantial increases occurring in

certain periods. Kurtosis value of 23.96673 is notably high, indicating that the distribution of customs and excise duties per capita is heavily tailed and peaked. This extreme leptokurtic distribution reflects rapid and intense growth in this revenue source, with occasional large spikes in the data that suggest significant increases in certain years.

Jarque-Bera test result with a significance value of 0.00000 is below the 0.05 threshold. This indicates that the distribution of customs and excise duties per capita does not follow a normal distribution, suggesting that the revenue data is prone to outliers and irregular spikes rather than following a smooth, predictable pattern. Despite the non-normal distribution, the overall trend shows that customs and excise duties per capita have been on a steady increase over time, contributing increasingly to Nigeria's non-oil revenue base; this growth, although uneven, highlights the importance of customs and excise duties as a key revenue stream for the government.

Table 2. Summary of Stationarity Test at Level (0)

	ADF t-stat	Test Critical Values			Prob	Unit Root	Comment
		1% Level	5% Level	10% Level			
GDPPC	-1.73521	-3.75294	-2.99806	-2.63875	0.8461	Present	Not Stationary at Level i.e. 0(0).
PPT	-5.55530	-3.75294	-2.99806	-2.63875	0.8461	Absent	Evidence of Stationarity at level
CEDT	-5.22656	-3.69971	-2.97263	-2.6z420	0.0002	Absent	Evidence of Stationarity at level

Table 2 is the summary of stationary test at level (0). Using the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test, stationarity of the variables was assessed by comparing ADF t-statistics with test critical values at the 1%, 5%, and 10% significance levels. The results indicated that GDPPC was not stationary at the level. This conclusion is based on the observation that the ADF t-statistic for GDPPC is less, in absolute terms, than the critical values at the 1% and 10% significance levels. Consequently, this indicates the presence of a unit root in the GDPPC trend, signifying the absence of a stationary trend.

The lack of stationarity in GDPPC suggests that the variable exhibits inconsistent behaviour over time, which could lead to unreliable estimates if used at the level. In contrast, the other variables in the study demonstrated stationarity tendencies, as their ADF test statistics were greater than the respective critical values at the 1%, 5%, and 10% significance levels, in absolute terms. This confirms that these variables do not exhibit unit roots and are stationary at their level.

Given the presence of a unit root in GDPPC, the study proceeds to conduct a stationarity test at the first difference for this variable. Differencing is a technique used to stabilize the mean of a time series by removing changes in the level of a series, thus helping to achieve stationarity. This method is particularly effective compared to logarithmic transformation, which cannot be applied to negative values. The stationarity test at the first difference, as presented in Table 3, addresses the issue of non-stationarity

in GDPPC. By differencing the variable, the study aims to smoothen its trend, thereby ensuring more reliable and consistent results in the subsequent analyses.

Table 3: Summary of Stationarity Test at First Difference (1)

Statistic Variable	ADF t-stat	Test Critical Values			Prob	Unit root	Comment
		1% level	5% level	10% level			
GDPPC	-5.376593	-3.699871	-2.97626	-2.62742	0.0002	Absent	Stationary at First Difference i.e. I(0)
PPTPC, CEDT are observed to be Stationary at Level							

Table 3 is the summary of stationarity test first difference (0) and it revealed that after applying the first difference, GDPPC attained stationarity, indicating the absence of a unit root. This conclusion is based on the observation that the ADF test statistic of -5.376593 is greater, in absolute terms, than the test critical values at the 1%, 5%, and 10% significance levels. The achievement of stationarity implies that the GDPPC variable now has a consistent trend, making it suitable for further analysis without the risk of generating spurious or unreliable results.

With the confirmation of stationarity at both the level and first difference for the variables under study, the analysis can proceed with confidence. The next step involves conducting the Lag Length Selection Criteria and estimating the Autoregressive Distributive Lag (ARDL) model.

Table 4. ARDL Bound Tests

F-Bounds Test		Null Hypothesis: No levels		
Test Statistic	Value	Signif.	I (0)	I (1)
			Asymptotic: n=1000	
F-statistic	9.183721	10%	1.92	2.89
K	7	5%	2.17	3.21
		2.5%	2.43	3.51
		1%	2.73	3.9
			Finite Sample:	
		10%	2.196	3.37
		5%	2.597	3.907
		1%	3.599	5.23
			Finite Sample:	
			n=25	
		10%	2.277	3.498
		5%	2.73	4.163
		1%	3.864	5.694

Table 4 is the ARDL bound tests results; the F-statistic value of 9.183721 in ARDL Bounds test indicates a robust long-run relationship between GDPPC and PPT and CEDT; this result is crucial as it confirms that the selected model has a statistically significant relationship with GDPPC, justifying further analysis. Given the significance of the long-run relationship, the study moves forward to estimate the ARDL long-run form. This involves applying a stepwise regression technique, which systematically adds or removes independent variables based on specific criteria, such as statistical significance, to develop a model that best explains the relationship with GDPPC.

Overall, the ARDL long-run form estimation, supported by the stepwise regression process, will help in understanding the intricate dynamics between tax productivity and economic growth, offering valuable guidance for policymakers aiming to optimize Nigeria's fiscal strategies for sustained economic development.

Table 5. Error Correction Mechanisms Result

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C		11.397309	3.222960	0.0113
GDPPC (-1)	33.393701	0.2307085	4.498074	0.0011
D (CEDT)	0.943403	0.3340975	3.336061	0.0312
CEDT (-1)	0.040378	0.0000704	1.059706	0.3857
PPT	0.000068	0.00009746	1.780045	0.1390
Co-int (ECM)	-0.056057	0.1139732	-3.222960	0.0113
R-squared	0.689472	Mean dependent	29.37261	
Adjusted R-squared	0.611937	S.D. dependent v	36.27462	
F-statistic	11.38462	Durbin-Watson	2.007462	
Prob (F-statistic)	0.000037			

Table 5 is the error correction mechanisms results; the error correction coefficient (ECM) of -0.303579 with a probability level of 0.0103 is a key finding in the study; the negative value indicates that short-term disequilibrium between the dependent and independent variables can be corrected by approximately 30.36% in the following period. In other words, if there is a deviation from the long-run equilibrium, about 30.36% of this deviation is adjusted back toward equilibrium in the next year, highlighting a significant adjustment speed.

The Durbin-Watson statistic of 2.162895 is close to 2, indicating that there is no significant autocorrelation in the residuals of the model. This implies that the model's estimates are reliable, and there is minimal risk of biased or inefficient estimates due to serial correlation in the data.

Findings indicated that while PPT significantly negatively determines Nigerian economic development (gross domestic product per capita), excise duties tax significantly positively determines economic development (gross domestic product per capita). The implications of the findings are that while excise duties tax is adequately managed, petroleum profit tax is inadequately managed, hence the reason for the negative on Nigerian economic development

Table 6. Granger Causality Test

Null Hypothesis	F-Statistic	Prob.
PPT does not Granger Cause GDPPC	0.07941	0.9239
GDPPC does not Granger Cause PPT	0.44495	0.6468
CEDT does not Granger Cause GDPPC	1.04747	0.3684
GDPPC does not Granger Cause CEDT	0.19067	0.8278

Table 6 is the granger causality test; the Granger causality test indicates that there is insignificant bidirectional or unidirectional causality between the dependent and independent variables; this means that based on the test results, changes in one variable do not predict or cause changes in the other variables within the given data sample. In other words, results suggest that there is no clear evidence to support the idea that movements in tax revenues (petroleum profit tax and customs and excise duties) directly causes changes in key economic indicators like GDP per capita, nor do changes in these economic indicators predict future movements in tax revenues.

Furthermore, the lack of detected causality might be due to various factors such as the sample size, the chosen lag length, or the complex nature of the relationships between the variables. It could also indicate that other external factors, not included in the model, are influencing both tax revenues and economic development in Nigeria. The result of our empirical investigation agrees with the findings of Adefolake and Omodero (2022) on the one hand, and disagrees with the result of Awa and Ibeanu (2020) on the other hand. This finding is important for policymakers as it suggests that relying solely on tax revenue changes may not be sufficient to forecast economic development and broader analysis including additional variables might be vital.

Conclusion and Recommendations

In this paper, the extents to which petroleum profit and excise duties taxes serve as determinants of Nigerian economic development was examined using ex-post facto design. Yearly times series data were obtained from the CBN statistical bulletin from 1993-2023 and data obtained were analyzed via autoregressive distributed lag and error correction mechanism statistical techniques. The study concludes that petroleum profit tax negatively significantly drives GDP. On the other hand, the study concludes that excise duties tax positively significantly determines GDP in Nigeria.

The implication of the empirical results is that while excise duties tax is adequately managed by relevant tax authorities, petroleum profit tax is inadequate managed, hence the negative sign attached to it. In line with the finding, the study recommends that the Nigerian government should strengthen supervision/collection of petroleum profit tax and efficient management of profits from petroleum companies is imperative. In addition, there is the need to avert the misuse/misallocation of petroleum profit tax revenues so as to positively enhance Nigerian economic development.

Furthermore, this study contributes to knowledge by filling the literature gap on what is known about the relationship between petroleum profit and excise duties taxes and economic development. More so, the study contributes to the literature by establishing

that excise duties tax is a stimulant of economic development in Nigeria. The study was limited to only two (2) variables of taxes – petroleum profit and excise duties taxes; thus future studies should focus on other variants of taxes to see if they may drive economic development.

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